

**FIRST DOCUMENTED ICHTHYOLOGICAL FAUNA OF THE DARER RIVER - A
TRIBUTARY OF RIVER TONS, DOON VALLEY, UTTARAKHAND**

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ABSTRACT

Over the course of a year, the fish fauna of the Darer River, a tributary of the River Tons in the District of Dehradun, was investigated. Ten species in all, representing two Orders, five Families, and ten genera, were identified. Family Cyprinidae was found to be the most dominant represented by with 3 species. According to IUCN characterization, 9 species fell under Least Concern category whereas only one species was found Vulnerable. Several anthropogenic stressors such as pollution from agricultural sources, human settlements, sewage and sewerage cause severe threat to the fish fauna and aquatic diversity of rivers. This is first attempt made to explore the fish faunal diversity of Darer River. Since this small study area is rich in its aquatic faunal diversity, hence its conservation must be given a priority.

Keywords: Fish fauna, Doon Valley, Darer River, Tons River.

INTRODUCTION

The aquatic ecosystem is important and it has large economic importance. Fresh water fishes give millions of the world's poorest people food and a means of subsistence, and via the export of commodities, they help enhance global economic well-being. The fish diversity is depending on biotic and abiotic factors. Fish communities also work as excellent biological indicators. Therefore, it is considered an important aspect of fishery potential of a water body.

Ichthyologists in India have shown an interest in topics such as fish assemblages influenced by environmental factors, fish assemblage variation between geographically defined regions, and spatial and temporal characterization of fish assemblages (Bhat, 2003, 2004; Sreekantha et al., 2009; Sarkar et al., 2010; Lakra et al., 2010; Shahnawaz et al., 2010; Vijaylakshmi et al., 2010; Jayaratne and Surasinghe, 2010; Sumith et al., 2011). The entire Himalayan system, in particular the Western Himalayan regions of Garhwal, Kumaon, and neighboring Himachal, have been researched for evaluating the fishing wealth from a range of perspectives (Johal et al, 2002; Nautiyal, 2005; Pathani and Upadhyay, 2006; Negi and Negi, 2010).

Doon Valley is endowed with a vast network of perennial rivers and hill streams, ponds, and reservoirs, which creates the perfect environment for a diverse range of fish species to thrive.

Doon Valley is geographically split into Eastern and Western Doon Valley. Fish research was conducted primarily in the Eastern Doon valley (Ganga drainage), according to a review of the literature. Notable researchers who contributed to this work were Hora and Mukerjee (1936), Lal and Chatterjee (1962), Singh (1964), Grover (1970), Mishra and Joshi (1970), Tilak and Husain (1973, 1976, 1977a, b, 1990), Husain (1985, 1987, 1995), Grover and Tripathi (1985), Husain and Tilak (1995), Grover et al. (1994), and Rauthan et al (2000). In 1964, Singh started surveying and

researching the Western Doon valley, which is part of the Yamuna drainage. Husain (1985, 1987, 1995) subsequently concentrated on specific areas. Recently, Uniyal et al. (2001, 2002, 2006), Bahuguna et al. (2001), Uniyal (2002), Uniyal and Kumar (2006), Uniyal and Mehta (2007), Gupta and Rana (2009a, b, c, d) and Chaudhary et al (2024) have conducted study on the fish and fisheries of the region.

To add more information to the existing fish faunal diversity of Doon Valley, an attempt was made to explore the diversity of Darer River which has not been attempted earlier.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Darer River is an intermittent stream in Uttarakhand and has an elevation of 563 metres. Darer River is situated nearby to Bāmi Rao, and west of Ghulaita Nadi. Darer River is an intermittent stream which is located in Uttarakhand nearby to Sudhonwala Tarla, Thakurpur Tarla and Bami Rao. It is also nearby Thakurpur and Sudhonwala Tarla. The latitude of Darer River is 30.34063, and the longitude is 77.93602 with the GPS coordinates of 30° 20' 26.26" N and 77° 56' 09.67" E (Fig.1). From November 2018 to October 2019, fish samples were collected at several sampling locations utilizing a variety of fishing nets and traditional equipment. Fish were tested in the wild and in a lab, respectively, in both fresh and preserved conditions. In line with the standard literature and revisionary works that are currently available, fish samples were preserved in 4% formalin and brought to the lab for standard identification, meristic, and morphometric analyses (Day, 1878; Jayaram, 1981, 1999; Talwar and Jhingran, 1991; Vishawanath et al., 2007 Nelson, 2016).

Fig. 1: Location of the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 10 species belonging to 2 Orders, 5 Families and 10 Genera were recorded. Darer River has not been explored earlier for its fish fauna. Table-1 represents the collected, examined and identified fish species along with their common names, family and IUCN categorization. A total of 10 species belonging to 2 Orders, 5 Families and 10 Genera were recorded. Family Cyprinidae was found to be the most dominant with 3 species. An assessment of family representation (Hora and Mukherjee, 1936; Uniyal and Kumar, 2006; Uniyal and Mehta, 2007) indicates that the Cyprinidae family dominates the Doon Valley and the Eastern and Western drainages in particular. This is in line with previous observations from the Himalayas and the Doon Valley (Grover et al., 1994; Uniyal, 2002; Johal, 2002; Nautiyal, 2005 Pathani and Upadhyay, 2006; Negi and Negi, 2010b) or other regions of the country (Bhat, 2003, 2004; Lakra et al., 2010; Shahnawaz et al., 2010) as well as overseas (Jayaratne and Surasinghe, 2010; Sumith et al., 2011).

According to IUCN characterization, 9 species fell under Least Concern category whereas only one species was found Vulnerable. Fish diversity has been given a specific category (Endangered, Vulnerable, Least Concern, or Near Threatened) based on internationally recognised standards established under CAMP (1998) and IUCN (15-4), according to Sreekantha et al. (2007) and Sarkar et al. (2010). When the fish fauna of the Doon valley was discussed in the past, the similar approach was taken (Uniyal et al., 2002; Uniyal and Kumar, 2006; Uniyal and Mehta, 2007).

Table 1. Fish Fauna of the Darer River, Dehradun.

S. No.	Common name	Scientific name	Family	IUCN Status
Order: Cypriniformes				
1.	Mottled loach	<i>Acanthocobitis botia</i> (Hamilton,1822)	Nemacheilidae	LC*
2.	Guntea loach	<i>Lepidocephalichthys guntea</i> (Hamilton,1822)	Cobitidae	LC
3.	Sucker head	<i>Garra gotyla</i> (Gray,1830)	Cyprinidae	LC
4.	Ticto barb	<i>Pethia ticto</i> (Hamilton,1822)	Cyprinidae	LC
5.	Hamilton's barila	<i>Opsarius bendelisis</i> (Hamilton,1807)	Danionidae	LC
6.	Vagra baril	<i>Barilius vagra</i> (Hamilton,1807)	Danionidae	LC
7.	Mola carplet	<i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> (Hamilton,1822)	Danionidae	LC
8.	Common Snowtrout	<i>Shizothorax richardsonii</i> (Gray,1832)	Cyprinidae	VU [#]
Order: Siluriformes				
9.	Indian gagata	<i>Gagata cenia</i> (Hamilton,1822)	Sisoridae	LC
10.	River cat	<i>Glyptothorax pectinopterus</i> (McClelland, 1842)	Sisoridae	LC

*LC - Least Concern, [#]VU - Vulnerable

CONCLUSION

The present investigation demonstrates good fish species availability. It might be connected to the proper ecology of the water body.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Dr. Deepali Rana conceptualized the manuscript and searched the literature. Dr. Dhyal Singh and Dr. Deepali Rana compiled the table and figures. Dr. Rahul Rana prepared the initial draft of the manuscript. The manuscript was proof edited by Dr. Deepali Rana and Dr. Ganesh Datt Bhatt.

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